

Triazoles as Complexing Agents : Synthesis and Characterisation of some Bivalent Metal with Bi- and Tridentate Schiff Bases

S. N. DUBEY* and BEENA K. VAID

Department of Chemistry, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra-132 119

Manuscript received 31 October 1990, revised 20 July 1992, accepted 31 July 1992

Schiff base complexes have been studied extensively¹. The Schiff base derived from AEMT and benzaldehyde has been reported to form complexes with some metal ions². In view of the above, it was thought of interest to synthesise and characterise the Schiff bases, EMST, EHNMT and DBEMT, and their complexes with Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II}.

Results and Discussion

The compounds are insoluble in common organic solvents and do not melt even upto 300°. Yields of the complexes are in the range of 70–80%.

Infrared spectra : The Schiff bases, EMST, EHNMT and DBEMT can exist in tautomeric thione and thiol forms and hence give characteristic thioamide bands in their ir spectra. The existence of thione form of the ligands has been proposed on the basis of a broad band around 3 100 cm⁻¹ (NH) and around 1 150 cm⁻¹ (C=S). A very weak band at 2 560–2 550 cm⁻¹ suggests thiol form. The high intensity bands at 1 620 cm⁻¹ are due to $\nu_{N=CH}$ and at 1 285 cm⁻¹ due to phenolic C–O vibration.

The changes observed in the metal complexes are as follows. (i) The band around 2 560–2 550 cm⁻¹ (SH) is absent indicating deprotonation of thiol group and formation of metal sulphur bond³

which is further confirmed by the appearance of a band at 380–340 cm^{-1} . (ii) Stretching frequency of C=S shifts towards lower side (1115–1065 cm^{-1}) indicating conversion of C=S into C–S and coordination of metal through sulphur atom. (iii) The band at 1620 cm^{-1} in ligand spectra shifts towards lower wavenumber (1610 to 1590 cm^{-1}) suggesting the coordination through nitrogen atom of the azomethine group and formation of metal-nitrogen bond⁴. It was further confirmed by appearance of band at 550–520 cm^{-1} . (iv) The vibrations due to phenolic group $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ appeared in 1320–1300 cm^{-1} region in 1:1 complexes as compared to 1280 and 1285 cm^{-1} observed for free ligands EMST and EHNMT respectively. It indicated deprotonation of phenolic OH groups and formation of metal-oxygen bond. However, in case of 1:2 complexes, deprotonation does not take place. The presence of OH group in 1:2 complexes of EMST was confirmed by the appearance of a band at 3400–3360 cm^{-1} . The presence of coordinating water in complexes is indicated by a broad band at 3400–3200 cm^{-1} , and somewhat weaker bands in the regions 800–750 and 720–700 cm^{-1} , assigned as the OH stretching, rocking and wagging vibrations⁵. From the above discussion, bidentate (N and S donor atoms) nature of DBEMT and tridentate (O, N and S donor atoms) nature of EMST and EHNMT are indicated.

Electronic spectra: Co(EHNMT).3H₂O gave the absorption bands at 9430; 13160; 15340 and 21270 cm^{-1} . The first band is assigned to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1) and the band at 21270 cm^{-1} due to ${}^4T_{1g}(E) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3) transitions. The second band usually observed in the region 13000–18000 cm^{-1} splits into two bands at 13160 and 15340 cm^{-1} which is assigned to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ (ν_2) transition. The band at 13160 cm^{-1} can arise due to low components to the ligand field or through the spin-forbidden transition. Co(EMST).3H₂O gave bands at 9260; 13300; 15360 and 21280 cm^{-1} . Co(EMST)₂ gave three bands at 9920; 13330; 15630 and 27027 cm^{-1} attributed to ν_1 , ν_2 and ν_3 transitions respectively. Thus, the transitions mentioned above are typical of six-coordinated complexes⁶.

Ni(EHNMT).3H₂O of octahedral geometry⁶ exhibits two bands at 13333 and 21730 cm^{-1} due to two spin-allowed transitions, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1) and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2), respectively. Ni(EMST).3H₂O complex also exhibits two bands at 13700 and 17240 cm^{-1} . In case of Ni(DBEMT).2H₂O, three bands observed at 11110; 18520 and 25640 cm^{-1} are assigned to three spin-allowed transitions for six-coordinated octahedral geometry. Bands observed at 21650 and 20000 cm^{-1} for Cu(EHNMT).H₂O and Cu(EMST).H₂O complexes respectively suggest square-planar geometry⁷.

Magnetic measurement: The effective magnetic moments (Table 1) for the Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes are well within the range expected for

spin-free complexes and also support the geometry mentioned earlier. In Cu(DBEMT).2H₂O, Cu^{II} gets reduced to Cu^I in presence of excess of ligand and hence indicates diamagnetic behaviour.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd. (Colour)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			μ_{eff}^* B.M
	M	C	H	
C ₁₁ H ₁₂ N ₄ OS (EMST) (White)	—	54.08 (53.22)	5.06 (4.83)	—
(C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₄ OS)Co.3H ₂ O (Reddish brown)	15.82 (16.42)	36.14 (36.77)	4.47 (4.45)	4.45
(C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₄ OS)Ni.3H ₂ O (Green)	16.40 (16.36)	37.04 (36.79)	4.36 (4.46)	2.92
(C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₄ OS)Cu.H ₂ O (Dark green)	20.02 (19.38)	39.53 (40.30)	3.75 (3.66)	2.09
(C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₄ OS)Zn.H ₂ O (White)	18.32 (18.82)	39.73 (40.08)	3.23 (3.64)	D
(C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₄ OS) ₂ Co (Reddish brown)	9.70 (10.69)	46.39 (47.91)	4.09 (3.36)	4.97
(C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₄ OS) ₂ Ni (Green)	10.85 (10.62)	46.14 (47.93)	4.47 (3.63)	3.2
(C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₄ OS) ₂ Cd (White)	18.50 (18.59)	44.15 (43.67)	4.07 (3.30)	D
C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₄ OS (EHNMT) (Yellow)	—	59.88 (60.40)	4.45 (4.69)	—
(C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₄ OS)Co.3H ₂ O (Reddish brown)	15.15 (14.41)	45.01 (44.01)	4.65 (4.40)	4.63
(C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₄ OS)Ni.3H ₂ O (Brown)	13.96 (14.36)	45.98 (44.09)	4.62 (4.40)	2.80
(C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₄ OS)Cu.H ₂ O (Dark green)	16.32 (16.82)	47.53 (47.68)	4.09 (3.70)	1.72
(C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₄ OS)Zn.H ₂ O (Yellow)	16.31 (16.43)	46.13 (45.30)	4.30 (4.02)	D
(C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₄ OS)Cd.H ₂ O (White)	26.37 (26.36)	43.66 (42.21)	3.46 (3.28)	D
C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₆ S (DBEMT) (Yellow)	—	56.45 (56.72)	6.08 (6.18)	—
(C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₆ S) ₂ Co.2H ₂ O (Grey)	9.01 (9.16)	48.03 (48.52)	5.28 (5.59)	4.77
(C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₆ S) ₂ Ni.2H ₂ O (Green)	8.93 (9.13)	48.52 (48.54)	5.20 (5.60)	3.51
(C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₆ S)Cu.2H ₂ O (Light yellow)	16.56 (17.03)	41.32 (41.74)	5.37 (5.35)	D
(C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₆ S) ₂ Zn.2H ₂ O (White)	10.27 (10.05)	47.87 (48.65)	5.51 (5.54)	D
(C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₆ S) ₂ Cd.2H ₂ O (White)	16.00 (16.14)	44.75 (44.80)	5.08 (5.16)	D

*D ≡ diamagnetic.

Epr spectra: The epr spectra of the Cu^{II} complexes of EHNMT and EMST were studied. The g_{\parallel} , g_{\perp} values have been found to be 2.20, 2.031; 2.16 and 2.06 respectively. The g_{av} values of 2.087 and 2.093 for these complexes were calculated according to the equation $g_{\text{av}} = 1/2(g_{\parallel} + 2g_{\perp})$. The observed g -values showed that the unpaired electron resides in $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital with $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp} > 2$ for square-planar geometry. The g_{\parallel} values are less than 2.3 thereby indicating the covalent nature of metal-ligand bonding⁸.

Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes: All the Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes are diamagnetic as expected for d^{10} -system. The Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes are four- as well as six-coordinated as inferred from elemental analyses and spectral data.

Thermal analyses: Thermal behaviour of the complexes is almost the same, hence thermal analyses of only two complexes, Co(EHNMT).3H₂O and Cd(EMST)₂ are discussed. In case of Co(EHNMT).3H₂O, two water molecules were lost in two clear steps at 80° and 160° corresponding to mass losses of 4.8% (4.4% theoretical) and 9.1% (8.8% theoretical). However, the third water molecule is lost at 265° with the required mass loss of 12.3% (13.2% theoretical) supported by slight endothermic effect on DTA curve. After this, the organic part of the complex starts decomposing gradually up to 400°, and at 450°, CoO and SO₂ may be formed as shown by exothermic effect on DTA curve and the corresponding mass loss on TG curve is 67.1% (66.0% theoretical). The total mass loss of 82.2% (81.7% theoretical) at 930° indicates the formation of metal oxide as the residue. Thermal degradation of the complex is given as

The anhydrous complex Cd(EMST)₂ is almost stable up to 170° and then organic part decomposes giving CdS and SO₂ at 500° indicated by the exothermic peak on DTA curve and mass loss of 65.1% (65.4% theoretical). Finally, at 880°, CdO is obtained as the residue requiring the total mass loss of 77.2% (78.3% theoretical). Thermal degradation of the compound is given as

Experimental

4-Amino-3-ethyl-5-mercapto-*s*-triazole (AEMT) was prepared following the literature method⁹. Schiff bases were prepared by refluxing equimolar quantities of AEMT and the corresponding aldehydes in ethanol for 2 h. The Schiff bases (Table 1) were recrystallised from ethanol. EMST was obtained as white compound (m.p. 180°; 70%), EHNMT as brown shining crystals (m.p. 235°; 60%) and DBEMT as yellow needle-like crystals (m.p. 215°; 65%). The spectral data of Schiff bases are as follows: C₁₁H₁₂N₄OS (EMST), ν_{max} (nujol) 3 120 (N-H and aromatic C-H), 1 610 (N=CH), 1 280 (C-O) (phenolic), 1 160 (C=S) and 900 cm⁻¹ (N-N); δ (acetone-d₆) 1.35 (3H, t, CH₂CH₃), 2.9 (2H, q, CH₂CH₃), 6.9-7.8 (5H, m, ArH and N=CH) and 11.2 (1H, SH); C₁₅H₁₄N₄OS (EHNMT), ν_{max} (nujol) 3 100 (NH), 1 620 (N=CH), 1 280 (C-O) (phenolic), 1 170 (C=S) and 890 cm⁻¹ (N-N); δ (acetone-d₆) 1.35 (3H, t, CH₂CH₃), 2.85 (2H, q, CH₂CH₃), 7.1-8.4 (7H, m, six ArH and N=CH), OH and SH could not be detected; C₁₃H₁₇N₅S (DBEMT), ν_{max} (nujol) 3 080 (N-H and aromatic CH), 1 615 (N=CH) and 1 160 cm⁻¹ (C=S); δ (acetone-d₆) 1.15 (3H, t, CH₂CH₃), 2.65 (2H, q,

CH₂CH₃), 2.95 (6H, s, -N(CH₂)₂), 6.72 (2H, d, ArH), 7.65 (2H, d, ArH), 9.15 (1H, s, N=CH) and 9.48 (1H, s, SH, disappeared on D₂O exchange). From the pmr spectra, it is evident that the thiol form exists in solution.

(3-Ethyl-5-mercapto-4-salicylideneamino-*s*-triazolo)cobalt(II) trihydrate (CoL.3H₂O); bis-(3-ethyl-5-mercapto-4-salicylidene-amino-*s*-triazolo)cobalt(II) (CoL₂) (L=EMST): Aqueous solutions of cobalt(II) acetate (AnalaR) were treated with hot ethanolic solution of the ligand (EMST) in 1:1 and 1:2 (metal:ligand) molar ratios. Precipitation occurred immediately. Heating was continued for ~ 0.5 h. The precipitates were washed with hot distilled water, ethanol and 50% acetone and then dried at 60-70°. Reaction in 1: excess molar ratios (Co^{II}:ligand) resulted in the formation of 1:2 complex.

Reactions with other metal acetates (AnalaR), namely Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} with the ligand (EMST) were carried out as above. In case of Ni^{II}, when the reaction was carried out in 1: excess molar ratio, the product was found to have 1:2 stoichiometry.

Reactions of different metal acetates with the ligands EHNMT and DBEMT were carried out separately under similar conditions. With EHNMT, the resulting complexes were of only 1:1 stoichiometry. The products with DBEMT were found to have 1:2 stoichiometry except Cu^{II} which had 1:1 stoichiometry. The metals in the complexes (Table 1) were estimated using standard procedures¹⁰.

IR spectra were recorded on a Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer, pmr spectra on a Perkin-Elmer spectrometer (90 MHz) and electronic spectra and epr spectra were recorded at I.I.T., Madras. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out at room temperature (25 ± 5°) with the help of vibrating sample magnetometer (model 155) at U.S.I.C., University of Roorkee, Roorkee, and magnetic corrections were applied¹¹. Thermal analyses were carried out on a Paulik-Paulik-Erdy OD-102 derivatograph. The specimens were heated at a rate of 10°/min in 20-1000° range and heated alumina was used as the standard.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Chairman of the Department for facilities and one of them (B.K.V.) is thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for the award of a Senior Research Fellowship.

References

1. R. H. HOLM and M. J. O. CONNEV, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1971, **41**, 253; L. SACCONI, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1968, **4**, 199; S. N. PODDAR and A. K. SARKAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **45**, 979.
2. S. A. PATIL, B. M. BODIGER, S. M. KUDARI and V. R. KULKARNI, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1983, **8**, 238.
3. M. R. GAJENDRAGAD and U. AGARWALA, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1975, **28**, 763; I. SUZUKI, *Bull. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **35**, 1286, 1449.

NOTES

4. C. P. PRABHAKARAN and C. C. PATEL, *Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1969, **31**, 3316; P. GLUGHINSKY, G. M. MOCKLER and S. SINN, *Spectrochem. Acta*, 1976, **1287**.
5. J. FUJITA, K. NAKAMOTO and M. ROBAYASHI, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 3663.
6. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, London, 1963, pp. 275-361.
7. C. A. AGAMBAR and K. G. ORELL, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 897.
8. D. KIVELSON and R. NEIMAN, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1961, **35**, 149.
9. K. S. DHAKA, JAGMOHAN, V. K. CHADHA and H. K. PUJARI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1974, **12**, 288.
10. A. I. VOGEL, "Quantitative Inorganic Analyses", 4th ed., Longmans Green, London, 1978.
11. B. N. FIGGIS and J. LEWIS in "Modern Coordination Chemistry", eds. J. LEWIS and R. G. WILKINS, Interscience, New York, 1967, pp. 403, 406.